

A Multicenter Study on the Prevalence of Antibiotic Resistance and Serotypes in Invasive and Nasopharyngeal Streptococcus Pneumoniae Isolates

Subhradeep Majumder¹, Jugal Kishor Agarwal²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Microbiology, School of Medical Sciences and Research, Sharda University, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India

²Associate Professor, Department of Microbiology, Rama Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Hapur, Uttar Pradesh, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Jugal Kishor Agarwal

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Abstract:

Introduction and Aims: Streptococcus pneumoniae is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. As epidemiological data regarding incidence of pneumococcal disease and antimicrobial susceptibility of pneumococci is scarce from developing countries, aim was to determine antimicrobial resistance patterns of pneumococcal isolates and correlate with the type of pneumococcal disease and serotypes.

Methods: Retrospective study, S. pneumoniae isolates were recovered from clinical and nasopharyngeal (NP) specimens from two tertiary care hospitals during January 2022-June 2024. Identification was done by standard microbiological procedures. Antimicrobial susceptibility, using disk diffusion was performed for chloramphenicol, trimethoprim-sulphamethoxazole (TMP-SMX) and vancomycin. MICs for penicillin, azithromycin, levofloxacin, and ceftriaxone were determined by E-test. Selected isolates were serotyped using type/group-specific antisera.

Results: A total of 153 non-duplicate pneumococcal isolates (51, 63, 10, 7 and 22 from pneumonia, pneumonia with concomitant sepsis, meningitis, other clinical isolates and NP carriage respectively) were collected. All meningeal and NP isolates were susceptible to penicillin and ceftriaxone (MIC 0.006-0.125 mcg/ml). Among non-meningeal isolates, penicillin and ceftriaxone susceptibility was 97.5% and 96.6% respectively (CLSI), 70.2% and 90.8% respectively (EUCAST). High level of resistance was observed to levofloxacin and TMP-SMX among both clinical (13%) and NP (38.9%) isolates. MDR was observed in 7.6% clinical isolates, 2 were pan-resistant. Mortality rate was 10%; all had at least one underlying disease. Most prevalent serotypes were 19F, 1, 7F, 12F, 18 (clinical samples) and 19F (NP carriage).

Conclusion: S. pneumoniae remains susceptible to penicillin. Emergence of non-beta-lactams and multidrug resistance among S. pneumoniae requires continuous monitoring of resistance, restricted use of antibiotics and to focus attention on pneumococcal vaccination.

Keywords: Antibiotic Resistance, Invasive Pneumococcal Disease, Invasive Pneumococcal Vaccines, Streptococcus Pneumonia.

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Introduction

Streptococcus pneumoniae is a leading infectious cause of invasive diseases, including pneumonia, bacteremia and meningitis among children and adults worldwide.[1,2,3] Mortality rate for invasive pneumococcal disease (IPD) is approximately 10 to 20% with even higher rates for elderly and immunocompromised individuals.[4,5].

Pneumococcal disease is commonly preceded by asymptomatic colonization of the nasopharynx especially in children. [5,6] There are about 90 serotypes based on antigenic differences in polysaccharide capsule and majority of IPD are caused by a relatively limited number of serotypes

[5] Penicillin remains the drug of choice for treatment of IPD. With the introduction of PPV in 1977, there was a significant reduction in the incidence of IPD. However, significant high level resistance to penicillin emerged in Europe during the early 1980's, and in US in the 1990's. Since then, penicillin resistance has rapidly spread worldwide with an increasing trend towards invasive disease associated with pneumococcal resistance to multiple classes of antimicrobial agents including penicillin.

About 15-30% of S. pneumoniae worldwide are multidrug-resistant (MDR) [7] Reports of penicillin

resistance rates among *S. pneumoniae* are as high as 80% in some regions of Asia [8,9]. Till date, very few data are available on the prevalence of invasive disease, serogroup/types and drug resistant *S. pneumoniae* (DRSP) from India. Interestingly, although the available data suggests that India still has low rates of penicillin nonsusceptible as well as MDR pneumococcal strains, trends of emerging resistance to beta-lactams is alarming. Surveillance studies of antimicrobial susceptibility rates for *S. pneumoniae* in Asian countries by ANSORP showed increase in prevalence of penicillin non-susceptible *S. pneumoniae* (PNSSP) from 1.48% during 1993-97 to 7.8% during 2000-2001 among Indian clinical isolates. [8,10] These were although represented by isolates from a single centre from South India. As increasing prevalence of DRSP is associated with increasing incidence of IPDs in children and high rates of therapeutic failures, [10] periodic monitoring of emergence of drug resistance is important. The present study was therefore conducted to evaluate the antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of clinical *S. pneumoniae* isolates and correlate with the type of pneumococcal disease.

Material and Methods

During the 2.6 year study period of January, 2022 to June, 2024 data was retrospectively collected of routine pneumococcal isolates recovered from clinical microbiology laboratories of 2 tertiary care hospitals in Uttar Pradesh. School of Medical Sciences and Research, Sharda University, is a 1200 bedded tertiary care teaching and referral hospital serving wide range of population in and around Greater Noida and adjoining areas of Delhi Haryana and Uttar Pradesh states. Rama Medical College Hospital and research centre is a 1000 bedded tertiary care hospital primarily catering to population in Hapur, Ghaziabad, Meerut and adjoining areas of UP. A total of 153 *S. pneumoniae* isolates were recovered from clinical and nasopharyngeal (NP) specimens from the two centres.

Isolate Identification and Antimicrobial Susceptibility tests: Specimens other than blood and CSF were plated on 5% sheep blood agar and MacConkey agar and incubated at 37°C in 5% CO₂ atmospheric condition. Blood and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) were cultured in in BacT/ALERT vials (Biomérieux, USA). Colonies morphologically consistent with *S. pneumoniae* were identified by optochin (5µg) susceptibility and were confirmed by both bile solubility test and latex agglutination with antisera.

In vitro antimicrobial susceptibility was performed for chloramphenicol, trimethoprim-sulpha methoxazole (TMP-SMX) and vancomycin by the disk diffusion method, according to the

performance standards from CLSI. [11] Pneumococcal isolates were screened for penicillin resistance using 1µg oxacillin disk (Himedia laboratories, Mumbai) and MIC was performed by E-test method according to manufacturer's instructions and interpreted as susceptible (MIC, ≤2 µg/mL), intermediate (MIC, 4 µg/mL) and resistant (MIC ≥8 µg/mL) for non-meningeal isolates and as susceptible (MIC, ≤0.06 µg/mL), resistant (MIC, ≥0.12 µg/mL) for meningeal isolates as per CLSI guidelines [11] (AB biodisk, Solna, Sweden). MICs for ceftriaxone, azithromycin and levofloxacin were also determined by E-test strips. *S. pneumoniae* ATCC 49169 was used as a control organism. Multi-drug-resistant (MDR) *S. pneumoniae* was defined as a strain resistant to at least three antimicrobial classes. [13] Multiple isolates from different sites of each patient were counted only once, and antimicrobial susceptibility of the first isolate was used in the present study. For the purpose of comparison, EUCAST breakpoints were also applied on the pneumococcal isolates. Selected isolates were serogrouped by Quellung capsular reaction using group/type-specific antisera [1,12].

The demographic data, primary source of bacteremia and underlying disease were compiled for analysis.

Results

A total of 153 *S. pneumoniae* strains isolated from the 2 study hospitals in Uttar Pradesh during January 2022 – June 2024 were included in the data evaluation. Of these, 129 strains were isolated from patients with invasive infections (79 and 50 contributed by 1st and 2nd center respectively) and 2 strains from non-invasive infection (conjunctivitis). 22 pneumococcal strains were isolated from nasopharynx of children (18 and 04 from 1st and 2nd centre respectively). Table 1A and 1B shows distribution of isolates in various clinical specimens. Briefly, of the 153 isolates, 51 were recovered from lower respiratory tract specimens (33.3%), 63 from blood cultures (41.2%), 10 from CSF (6.5%), and 7 from other specimens. CSF isolates were isolated only from neonates and children.

The ages of patients ranged from 6 days to 91 years.

Among invasive infections (n=129), the clinical presentation and chest X ray findings were suggestive of pneumonia in 114 patients (51 had isolated pneumococcal pneumonia and 63 had bacteremic pneumococcal pneumonia. No other primary source of bacteremia was detected. Ten patients presented with meningitis, and primary source was detected in only one case (pulmonary). All the nasopharyngeal isolates were considered to be representing nasopharyngeal carriage. 120 of the

129 patients with invasive clinical disease were hospitalized and 38 of these needed intensive care. Mortality was observed in 10% (13/129) patients and all these had at least one underlying disease (Diabetes Mellitus, Carcinoma). Mortality was seen irrespective of penicillin resistance or MDR, Children vs adults. Table 2 shows MIC results of isolates from patients with invasive infections and nasopharyngeal colonization for penicillin, ceftriaxone, levofloxacin and erythromycin 100% (22/22) of the nasopharyngeal isolates showed susceptibility to penicillin. 2% (1/51) pneumococcal isolate causing pneumonia was penicillin intermediate-resistant. One pneumococcal isolate from bacteremia showed a high level resistance with MIC of 8.0 µg/mL. 100% (10/10) of meningeal isolates were susceptible to penicillin. 95.9% (116/119) of non-meningeal and

100% (10/10) of meningeal isolates were susceptible to ceftriaxone. 31.8% (7/22) and 4.5% (1/22) of NP and 14.2% (17/120) and 24.2% (29/120) pneumonia isolates were non-susceptible to levofloxacin and erythromycin respectively. 100% (10/10) and 80% (8/10) of meningeal strains showed susceptibility to levofloxacin and erythromycin respectively. Susceptibility to TMP-SMX was observed in 66.9% (81/121), and 60% of pneumonia and meningeal isolates. 100% of NP isolates were TMP-SMX resistant. 92.5% (112/121) of pneumonia and 100% each of NP and meningeal isolates were susceptible to chloramphenicol. Multidrug resistance (MDR) was seen in 5.3% (7/131) of clinical isolates and in none of the NP isolates.

Table 1A: Distribution of samples center wise

Type of sample	1st Centre (SMSR Shar-da Univ.)	2 nd Centre (Rama Medical College)	Total
Invasive sample (Pneumonia, Bacteremia, Meningitis)	79	50	129
Non-invasive Samples (Conjunctival swab)	2	0	2
Nasopharyngeal samples	18	04	22

Table 1B: Sample wise distribution

Clinical syndrome	No. of samples
Lower Respiratory Tract Infection (Sputum, BAL, Tracheal)	51
Bacteraemia/Sepsis (Blood culture)	63
Meningitis (CSF)	10
Others- Otitis/ Sinusitis/ Septic arthritis (Ear Swab-2, Sinus wash-1, Synovial fluid-2)	5
Non-invasive Disease (Conjunctival swab)	2
Nasopharyngeal carriage (NP Swab)	22
Total	153

Table 2: Antimicrobial MICs for Pneumococcal isolates from clinical infections

Antimicrobial	Pneumococcal Pneumonia (n=51)		Pneumococcal Pneumonia Bacteremia (n=63)		Pneumococcal Meningitis (n=10)	Nasopharyngeal Carriage (n=22)
Penicillin						
MIC50	0.064		0.012		0.016	0.016
MIC90	1.0		0.25		0.032	0.064
RANGE	0.006-3.0		0.006-8.0		0.006-0.064	0.006-0.125
MEAN	0.066		0.021		0.014	0.016
Clinical Breakpoint	Non-meningeal	Meningeal	Non-meningeal	Meningeal	Meningeal	Non-meningeal
% NS	2	31.4	3.2	12.7	0	0
% S	98	68.6	96.8	87.3	100	100
Ceftriaxone						
MIC50	0.064		0.012		0.012	0.016
MIC90	0.5		0.094		0.023	0.064
RANGE	0.006-2.5		0.006-2.0		0.006-0.064	0.006-0.125
MEAN	0.057		0.018		0.013	0.016
Clinical Breakpoint	Non-meningeal	Meningeal	Non-meningeal	Meningeal	Meningeal	Non-meningeal
% NS	5.9	9.8	3.2	4.8	0	0

% S	94.1	90.2	96.8	95.2	100	100
Levofloxacin						
MIC50	0.5		0.5		0.125	0.5
MIC90	4.0		24		1.5	16
RANGE	0.006-32		0.006-94		0.094-2.0	0.006-32
MEAN	0.5		0.686		0.249	0.368
% NS	13.7		17.5		0	31.8
% S	86.3		82.5		100	68.2
Erythromycin						
MIC50	0.19		0.19		0.19	0.125
MIC90	16		1		0.38	0.25
RANGE	0.006-256		0.016-256		0.064-0.75	0.019-0.5
MEAN	0.217		0.202		0.18	0.103
% NS	23.5		25.4		20	4.5
% S	76.5		74.6		80	95.5
Chloramphenicol						
% NS	3.9		11.1		0	0
% S	96.1		88.9		100	100
TMP-SMX						
% NS	11.8		54		60	100
% S	88.2		46		40	0
Vancomycin						
% S	100		100		100	100

Table 3: Comparison of Antimicrobial susceptibility percentages applying CLSI and EUCAST clinical breakpoints

Antibiotic	CLSI				EUCAST			
	Non-meningeal (121)		Meningeal (10)		Non-meningeal (121)		Meningeal (10)	
	NS	S	NS	S	NS	S	NS	S
Penicillin	S ≤2; R ≥8		S ≤0.064; R ≥0.12		S ≤0.064; R ≥2		S ≤0.064; R ≥0.064	
	2	98	0	100	21.5	78.5	0	100
Ceftriaxone	S ≤1; R ≥4		S ≤0.5; R ≥2		S ≤0.5; R ≥2			
	4.1	95.9	0	100	6.6	93.4	0	100
Levofloxacin	S ≤2; R ≥8 (N=131)				S ≤2; R ≥2 (N=131)			
	NS		S		NS		S	
	13.7		86.3		14.9		85.1	
Erythromycin	S ≤0.25; R ≥1 (N=131)				S ≤0.25; R ≥0.5 (N=131)			
	22.7		76.3		25.6		74.4	

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

Penicillin G MIC in Non meningeal isolates

Figure 3:

Figure 4:

Figure 5:

Figure 6:

Figure 7:

Figure 8:

Table 4: Review of Penicillin Non-susceptibility and resistance to other antimicrobials among Pneumococcal isolates from India

Year of isolation	Location	Specimen	No .	Breakpoint applied	Pen I (%)	Pen R (%)	Levo (%)	Er (%)	Co (%)	MDR of total isolates (%)
2008 Reported [2]	Vellore	Blood*	01	S = ≤ 0.06 I = 0.12-1.0 R = ≥ 2	0	100 (MIC 2.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}^*$)	0	100 (MIC >32)	100 (MIC >4)	100
1999 [14]	Vellore	Clinical specimens	53	S = ≤ 0.06 I = 0.12-1.0 R = ≥ 2	4.6	0				0
2000-2001 [10]	Vellore (part of ANSORP Group***)	Clinical specimens	77	S = ≤ 0.06 I = 0.12-1.0 R = ≥ 2	7.8	0	1.3	1.3		
1998-1999 [15]	Vellore (part of ANSORP Group***)	NP carriage	98	S = ≤ 0.06 I = 0.12-1.0 R = ≥ 2	12.8	0	Not tested	0	59.2	Not specified
1996-1997 [8]	Vellore (part of ANSORP Group***)	Clinical specimen	183	S = ≤ 0.06 I = 0.12-1.0 R = ≥ 2	3.8	0	Not tested	0	33.3	Not specified
2008 [9]	Coastal Karnataka	Lower respiratory	50	S = ≤ 0.06 I = 0.12-1.0 R = ≥ 2	10	04	14	14		04
1999-2002 [16]	East Delhi	Clinical specimens, NP	170	S = ≤ 0.06 I = 0.12-1.0 R = ≥ 2	15.3	2.3	0+	0	55.2	12.9
2002 Reported [17]	Pondicherry	Clinical specimens	124	S = ≤ 0.06 I = 0.12-1.0 R = ≥ 2	11.6	0	1.6 ⁺	1.8	24	Not specified

2001 [Reported] [6]	Pondichery	Clinical specimens	150	S = ≤ 0.06 I = 0.12-1.0 R = ≥ 2	7.3					Not specified
2002-2003 [18]	New Delhi	Ophthalmic, systemic, NP	61	S = ≤ 0.06 I = 0.12-1.0 R = ≥ 2	0	0	29.5+	1.6	75.4	0
2010 [19]	Dibrugarh, Assam	NP	104	S = ≤ 0.06 I = 0.12-1.0 R = ≥ 2	0	17.1	0	0	57.7	0
2008-2009 [20]	Chennai, Hyderabad (part of ANSORP study)	Clinical specimens	23	S = ≤ 2.0 I = 4.0 R = ≥ 8.0	0	0 [^]	0	17.4	91.3	Not specified
				S = ≤ 0.06 I = 0.12-1.0 R = ≥ 2	30.4	0 [^]				
2022 [21]	Chandigarh	Clinical specimens, NP	68	S = ≤ 0.06 I = 0.12-1.0 R = ≥ 2	36.8	7.4	10.2	23.5	76.5	32

*considered meningial isolate, ** Ceftriaxone also resistant (1 mcg/ml), *** (Asian Network for Surveillance of Resistant Pathogens), + ciprofloxacin was tested, ^ ceftriaxone 4.4% resistant

Discussion

The increasing rate of pneumococcal disease is a big concern for the developing countries since the disease can directly alter the morbidity and mortality rate of a specific region. Pneumococcal diseases are broadly classified into two categories-invasive (Meningitis, Sepsis, Pneumonia) and non-invasive (which can get transformed into invasive type when associated with bacteraemia (22-24). Although both invasive and non-invasive pneumococcal diseases are curable but a number of associated factors (smoking, drinking, age, comorbidity, old age, air pollution etc) can increase the risk factor and cause death (25).

This study was performed for duration of total 2.6 years (from January, 2022 to June, 2024). The analysis of 153 *S. pneumoniae* isolates from the patients of age group 6 days to 91 years from two tertiary hospital of Northern India within the time period suggests that majority of strains (129) were isolated from patients with invasive infections, while the remaining were from non-invasive infections, such as conjunctivitis. Among the 153 *S. pneumoniae*, majority were isolated from either lower respiratory tract or blood samples indicating higher colonization of the organism in respiratory tissues and blood. Few samples were isolated from CSF especially patients with meningitis indicating the effective colonization of the organism in central nervous system. Among 153 isolates, 51 were responsible for pneumococcal pneumonia, 63 could cause pneumococcal pneumonic bacteremia, 10 isolates were responsible to form pneumococcal

meningitis and 22 isolates were responsible for pneumococcal carriage.

Upon performing antibiotic susceptibility test a striking result for MDR among many of the clinical isolates were observed. The susceptibility tests were performed against penicillin, ceftriaxone, levofloxacin, erythromycin, chloramphenicol, vancomycin and TMP-SMX. For nasopharyngeal and meningial isolates 100% susceptibility for Penicillin and Ceftriaxone respectively were observed.

The meningial isolates showed 100% susceptibility against Penicillin and Levofloxacin. MDR was observed among 5.3% which is 7 out of 131 clinical isolates. No MDR was reported from any of the NP isolates. The MIC results for both MIC50 and MIC90 showed in table 1 clearly indicate susceptibility of the organisms in low concentrations.

Table 4: highlights the susceptibility of *Streptococcus pneumoniae* isolates from varied specimens to antibiotics across India. For instance, it is observed throat specimen collected in 1999 from the regions of Vellore shows complete 100% resistance to both penicillin and erythromycin (with MIC >2.0 ug/ml and >32 ug/ml respectively). The blood specimen collected from Vellore in 2008 is also resistant to both penicillin and erythromycin resulting in multidrug resistant. MDR reduces treatment efficacy by provoking inhibition in disease control and hence, prolonged infection (26).

On the other hand, clinical samples and NP carriage isolates showed moderate or no MDR. 50

lower respiratory sample and 170 clinical specimen collected from coastal Karnataka and east Delhi showed 4% and 12.9% of isolates to be multi-drug resistant.

The tabular data provides insights that resistance patterns vary across regions and time periods, highlighting changing trends in antibiotic resistance. The data sorted based on the specimen type showed blood and throat specimens are highly resistant to penicillin and erythromycin with substantially high levels of MDR. However clinical and nasopharyngeal carriage showed minute instances of MDR with varied resistance patterns.

From the above data it can be concluded that the 2.6 year long had been a successful one for isolation of 153 isolates. The presence of >90% of isolates with susceptibility against commonly administered antibiotics is a good sign for clinical practitioners. However, the MDR of 5.3% of the clinical isolates is a big concern and needs further drug specific investigation.

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